

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	ZHY-1-24- IBN-5-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	15	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	ZHY 1 24
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	244.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 244.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/18/2022 15:03:55 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 20:34:43 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.795	490464	50.59	45025
2	8.495	479114	49.41	40408

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-128-IBN-5-2% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20221118
Vial:	16	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	lm 4 128
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	244.0nm
Run Time:	12.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 244.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/18/2022 18:02:27 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 20:36:01 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.656	68528	2.42	5612
2	8.285	2765072	97.58	246749